

THE INFLUENCE OF TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS AND ADAPTABILITY ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

Hauwa Ibrahim Adamu

School of Postgraduate and Sub-degree Programmes, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare, Bauchi State, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17339369>

Abstract

The study investigated teacher's effectiveness and adjustment level as predictor of student achievement in Katagum Local Government schools in Bauchi state. Three objectives and three hypotheses were postulated and tested in the study. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study and a simple random sampling technique was used to select 354 students from a population of 4500. The instrument used in the study were Teachers Effectiveness Questionnaire and adjustment scale. Inferential statistics of Linear Regression and Chi-square were used to analyze the data collected for the study. Based on the findings and the conclusion drawn from this study examine that teachers' effectiveness and adjustment significantly influenced academic achievement of students in senior secondary schools. The findings recommends among others that, teachers should be given adequate motivation and reinforcement as a way of making sure that they are motivated for effective teaching and educational practices. Teachers should always emphasize and encourage all eligible students to actively participate in Classroom teaching/learning. Teachers should also equip their students with adequate knowledge and proper guidance for them to adjust fully in the school environment.

Keywords: Teachers, Effectiveness, Adjustment, Predictor, Achievement

Introduction

Education is the means of bringing about meaningful development in the society. This is done through training of members of society there is need for a standard way of training and full knowledge on the material to be learn. This brings us to the effort of curriculum planners, government, educational administrators as well as teachers in realizing the goals of teaching and learning. In the school setting you find some students or learners are bring while others are dull, some display high intelligence while some display low intelligence. Some have high academic achievement while others have low. Teachers' effectiveness broadly means the collection of characteristics, competencies, and behaviours of teacher at all education levels that enable students to reach desired outcomes (Awong, 2012). Kagathela (2011) explain that an effective teacher is the one who has sense of humor, ability to explain thing clearly so that student can easily understand what is being taught, ability to make any subject interesting to learn, ability to control the class, ability to be ready and willing to help student when they are in need and ability to be as fair as possible in dealing with students. In Mangal (2011), explained adjustment as any operation whereby an organism or organ becomes more favorably related to the environment or to the entire situation. Adjustment refers to a harmonious relationship between the people or a students and the

environment, the degree of harmonious relationship between the people or a students and the environment, the degree of harmony depend upon two things: certain potentialities within a person and character of the environment. A person is said to be adjusted when he is so related to reasonably adequate environment that he is relatively happy, efficient and has a degree of social feeling and adjustment in education setting is the adaption of a students that make them to function effectively in the classroom situation in order to avoid failure (Dhillon, 2010). Teachers who are reasonably satisfied and adjusted are efficient and provide improvement in education. The level of adjustment of a teachers directly linked with efficiency in his work. Thomas (2010) said Teachers who are reasonably satisfied and adjustment and provide improvement in education. The level of adjustment of a teacher is directly linked with the efficiency in his work. The teacher besides intellectual activation, socially emerging and emotion integrating an individual, also takes the nation on the road of economic property, social uplift, industrial advancement. Adjustment helps a person in maintaining a balance between its need and the circumstance and influence the satisfaction of their needs (Kaur, 2011). Teachers means adjustment of teacher with their school environment, teachers with Academic and General Environment of the institution, Socio- psycho-physical Adjustment, professional relationship Adjustment, Personal life Adjustment, Financial Adjustment and job satisfaction. The success in teaching is significantly related to adjustment in various spheres of life including professional life (Rahman, 2011). There are many factors that influence student academic achievement. Student performance in school may be related to their personality and intelligence factors. Factors such as psychological and social motivation, attitude, self-concept, social adjustment, inadequate learning materials, teachers' competence, unsuitable learning environment, etc cannot be ignored. Several studies conducted by psychologist have shown that teachers primary role of transmission of knowledge and skills is never in dispute hence the adequacy and quality for better service delivery of teaching need to be assessed on a regular basis. Therefore, the performance of teachers should be glaring and persistent for their leaners have been faced with low academic performance being the fact that the teachers are not well skilled and passionate among the leaning. This extent and level of academic performance therefore borders on the quality of human material resources which are available during their schooling.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study are to;

1. Find out the combine influence of teachers effectiveness and adjusted on student academic achievement among senior secondary school in Katagum Local government area of Bauchi state.
2. Find out the relationship between teachers' effectiveness and senior secondary school students academic achievement in Katagum Local government area of Bauchi state.
3. Find out the relationship between adjustment and senior secondary school students academic achievement in Katagum Local government Area of Bauchi state.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were postulated in the study:

1. There is no significant combine influence of teachers’ effectiveness and adjustment on students’ academic achievement among senior secondary school in Katagum Local government area of Bauchi state.
2. There is no significant relationship between teachers’ effectiveness and senior secondary school students’ academic achievement in Katagum Local government area of Bauchi state.
3. There is no significant relationship between adjustment and senior secondary school students’ academic achievement in Katagum local government area of Bauchi state.

4. Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted in this study. The design concerned with the condition that exist, practice that prevail, beliefs and attribute of people. (Cohen and Menion, 2000). In support of the above view, Bichi (2004) added that descriptive survey specified who and what to be measured and it assesses people’s opinions toward situations. Most assessment such as evaluation studies are categorized as descriptive survey design. Nworgu (2006) is a design in which group of people or items is studied by collection and analyzing data from a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire group. The population of the study comprised all teachers in senior secondary schools in the twenty eight (28) senior secondary schools within Azare metropolis (public and private) in Katagum local government area, Bauchi state with total number of four thousand five hundred and twelve students (4500). (Katagum Zonal Education Office, Bauchi State, 2021). Simple random sampling procedure was used in reaching the sample for the study. The technique gives each element in the population equal and dependent chance of being included in the sample. A sample size is that pattern of the population being studied drawn through a definite procedure. From the population, the sample of ten (10) secondary schools were selected using random sampling with the sample size of three hundred and fifty four (354) student based on the recommendation by Kreycie and Morgan table for determining sample size. The table below shows the proportionate selected of students by school.

Table 2: Distribution of Sample

S/N	Sample School	Sample Student
1.	Government day secondary school Matsango	40
2.	Al-amin Academy Secondary school	39
3.	Government Technical college	30
4.	Government college	35
5.	Demonstration secondary school	30
6.	Baba kafinta Government day secondary	40
7.	Tatari Ali government day secondary school	35
8.	Abdullahi memorial secondary school school	30
9.	Fedral Government college	35
10.	Government day secondary school Matsango	40
	Total	354

Two instrument were used to collect data for this study; the Teachers' Efectiveness Questionnaire and The Adjustment Scale The teachers' effectiveness questionnaire (TEQ) the instrument used by Mackaeachie (1997) Crawford and Bradshaw (1968) and Awoyemi opined that the best subjective judgment of the criterion of teachers' effectiveness might be provide by the student course. Historically student rating have dominated as the primary measurement of teaching effectiveness for past 30 years (Seldin, 1999) Mackaeachie (1997) noted that student rating is most valid source of data on teaching effectiveness instrument is adopted by the researcher and used for this study to measure the teachers effectiveness in the study area. The instrument contained Thirty (30) items to be answered by the students making the sample within the study area. The Thirty items instrument is prepared to cover teachers' performance. Rate each teacher on the 1-5 basis in his or her activities listed (1-30) by putting a tick in one of the space on the scale according to the student view about the teachers performance. The scale: mean very poor (VP) from which the respondent to tick option that apply to them. The adjustment Scale (AS) modified and adopted from Basil (2010) which is the instrument for measuring students' school adjustments. The instrument contain twenty (20) item place on five liker scale of: (Strongly Agree-SA; agree-A; Undecided – UD; Disagree-D; strong Disagree-SD). The marks will be allocated to each of the responses ranges from 5-1 starting from strong strongly agree to strongly disagree. Data collected for the study were analyzed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 23.0. The result obtained from the research instrument filled by the respondents were correlated with the student result from the first or second term explain which is to be collected from their respective departments. Inferential statistics was used where the relationship between the variables.

Result

Table 1: Summary of the Level of Teaching Effectiveness

S/N	General effectiveness	Mean	Standard Deviation
1.	Classroom management	9.96	3.433
2.	Teaching technic and methods	5.19	2.749
3.	Personality	7.15	4.648
Average Result		7.43	3.610

Result in table 1 showed correlation statistics of the teaching effectiveness of Civic teachers in Katagum Local government Area of Buchi state. Considering the average result of the standard deviation, it can be drawn out from the table that level of teaching effectiveness in the study area is moderated at (SD+3.61).

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant combine influence of teachers' effectiveness and adjustment area on student academic achievement among senior secondary school in Katagum local government area of Bauchi state.

Table 2: Regression Analysis showing the relative combine Influence of Teachers’ Effectiveness and Adjustment on Students’ Academic Achievement among Senior Secondary School in Katagum Local Government Area of Bauchi state

Model	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean F-value Square	Sig. of f-value	Remark
Regressing	6840.705	6	1140.117		
Residual	120910.776	345	153.831	7.412 006	S
Total	127751.480	351			
R=.231 R square=.054			Adjusted R square=.021		

S: Significant at 0.05 alpha level of significance

Result in table 2 showed that there is significant relationship between teachers effectiveness and senior secondary school student academic achievement in the study area (F=4.096, p<0.05). Therefore the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between teachers’ effectiveness and senior secondary school students’ achievement in Civic in the study area is hereby rejected. The R value of 0.231 indicated a high degree of correlation between teachers R square value of 0.054 accounted for a low variation of 5.4% in teachers’ effectiveness and senior secondary school students’ academic achievement in the study area.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between teachers’ effectiveness and senior secondary school students’ academic achievement in Katagum local government area of Bauchi state.

Table 3: Relationship between Teachers’ Effectiveness and Senior Secondary School Students Academic Achievement

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R=value	P=value
Teachers effectiveness	354	29.9622	5.43312	.123	.001
Academic Achievement	354	53.1929	12.70049		

Table 3 above indicated relationship analysis between teachers’ effectiveness and Academic achievement. The number of respondent were 354 with mean score of teachers effectiveness of 29.9622 and standard deviation SD=5.43312 and that of academic achievement has 354 respondents with mean score 53.1929the standard deviation (SD) = 12.70049. The r. value is 123 and the P value .001 which is less than .05 level if significant relationship between teachers’ effectiveness and student Academic achievement.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between adjustment and senior secondary school students’ academic achievement in Katagum local government area Bauchi state.

Table 4: Relationship between Teachers’ Adjustment and Senior Secondary School Students Academic Achievement

Variables	N	Mean	SD	R=value	P=value
Adjustment	354	21.4122	2.3226	.213	.006
Academic achievement	354	53.1929	12.70049		

Table 4 above indicated relationship analysis between adjustment and academic achievement. The number of respondents were 354 with mean score of 21.4122 and standard deviation $SD=2.3226$ and that of academic achievement has 354 respondents with mean score 53.1929 the standard deviation (SD) = 12.70049, the r. value is .213 and the p. value .006 which is less than .05 level of significant. The above stated null hypothesis is rejected. It was concluded from this result that there is significant relationship adjustment and students' academic achievement.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it can therefore be concluded that teachers' effectiveness and adjustment have significant impact as predictors on senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Katagum local government area of Bauchi state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and the conclusion drawn, the following recommendations were put forward:

1. There should be opportunity by the government for the purpose of learning via seminars, conferences and training of teachers
2. Teachers should be given adequate motivation and reinforcement as a way of making sure that they are motivated for effective teaching and educational practices.
3. Teachers should always emphasize and encourage all eligible student to actively participate in classroom teaching/learning.
4. Teachers should equip their students with adequate knowledge and proper guidance for them to adjust fully in the school environment.

References

- Awong, M. Singh, B. & Dulkanaina, I. (2010). An Analysis of Relationship Effective Teaching Effective Learning. *Internal Journal of Education*. 4(12): 357 – 371.
- Dhillon, J.S & Navdeep, K. (2010). A Study of teacher effectiveness in relation to their value patterns recent researches in Education and psychology. 15, 5,111-1V.
- Hunt, B.C (2010). *Teacher Effectiveness: A Review of the International Literature and its Relevance for Improving Education in Latin America*. Washington, DC: PREAL.
- Kagathela, A. B (2011). A Study of Effectiveness of Teachers of Secondary School in Gujarat. *Journal of Educational Psychology*.
- Katagum Zonal Education Office (2021). Katagum LEA Schools Data.
- Kane, T.J. (2010). Learning Initial Finding from Measure of Effective Teaching. *Journal of human resource*, 3(2) 68-70.

Kaur, M. (2011). Teacher Effectiveness in relation to Self-concept of Elementary School Teachers. India Stream Research Journal; 1(3): 13-14

Mangal, S. K. (2011). Advanced educational Psychology. Learning Private Limited: New Delhi

Rahman, F. (2011). Relationship between training of teachers and effectiveness teaching. Indian journal business and social science 2(1): 150-160.

Shehu, M.T. (2011). Supervision and Teacher Effectiveness in Kwara State School for Special Needs, Illori, Kwara State. Unpublished M. Dissertation, University of Illorin.

Thomas, J. (2012). Identify Effective Classroom Practice using Student Achievement Data. Journal of Human Resources, 3(8): 143-159.

UNESCO (2004). Review of the Present Education Situation in Special Education, Web Accessed, [Http: unesco.org/pu.obj.cache](http://unesco.org/pu.obj.cache).

Orji, .N. (2014). Relationship between Science Teachers Classroom Management Effectiveness and Students' outcome in Chemistry. International Journal of Modern Education Research, 1(1): 11-14.

Oyekan, S.O. (2000). Foundations of Teacher Education. Okitipupa: Uluwa Press.

Stronge, J. H., Ward, T.J., & Grant L w (2011). What Makes Good Teachers Good! A Cross-case Analysis of the Connection between Teacher Effectiveness and Student Achievement. Journal of Teacher Education, 62(4): 339-355.